

Comparative Empirical Study between Public & Private Life Insurance Companies

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Abstract

The insurance sector, Along with other elements of marketing, as well as financial infrastructure, have been touched and influenced by the process of liberalization and globalization in India. The customer is the king in the market. Life insurance companies deal in intangible products. With the entry of private players, the competition is becoming intense. In order to satisfy the customers, every company is trying to implement new creations and innovative product characteristics to attract customers. With increase in population and income there is a wide scope in insurance sector and it was found that LIC plays an important role and has maximum share in this sector. Recently banking sector has also moved towards insurance sector since they would get better dividends than the commission they would get by entering into partnerships with other major insurance market players. The present study is an attempt to measure the various parameters as perspective by the customers and to help the insurance company (both public and private sector) in serving its customers in a much better and efficient manner.

Keywords: Insurance, LIC, Private Player, Customers and Innovation

Introduction

Insurance is defined as a cooperative device to spread the loss caused by a particular risk over number of persons who are exposed to in and who agree to ensure themselves against that risk. Risk is uncertainty of a financial loss. A well developed and evolved insurance sector is needed for economic development as it provides long term funds for infrastructure development and at the same time strengthens the risk taking ability. IRDA has till now provided registration to 12 private life insurance companies. Today the company image is built and made known by its customers. Thus the success of the insurance firm will be determined by how effective it has been in meeting the diverse consumer needs and wants by treating each customer as unique and offering products and services to suit his or her needs. Therefore today all the firms are engaged in a process of creating a lifetime value and relationship with their customers, a step towards developing knowledge regarding its customers needs is the utmost important. Keeping this in mind, the present study is designed to analyze the innovation in Life insurance sector in India.

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the comparison of various policies owned by the policy holders.
- To examine the problems faced by life insurance policy holders.

Research Methodology

Data Sources - Research is totally based on primary data. Secondary data can be used only for the reference. Research has been done by primary data collection, and primary data has been collected by interacting with various people through questionnaire. The secondary data has been collected through various journals and websites.

Sampling Procedure - The sample was comprised of the customers of public or private life insurance providers. It was also collected through personal interview, by formal and informal talks and through filling up the questionnaire prepared.

Sample Size - The sample size is limited to 100 people only. Out of which 76 customers were of Public life insurance company (LIC) and 24 customers were of Private life insurance companies.

Sampling Method - Judgement convenience method was used to select sample.

Statistical Tools Used - The data has been analyzed by using Statistical tool. Statistical tools like averages, percentages, Z- test, mean and standard deviation are used for the analysis of data.

Analysis and Interpretation of Survey Data

The demographic profile of the respondents analyzed on the basis of age, educational qualification, occupation and annual income.

Table - 1 Age Group Distribution of Respondents

Age Group	No. of respondents	Percentage to the Total
25- 35 years	36	36%
36-45 years	44	44%
46 -55 years	17	17%
Above 60 years	3	3%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

It is clear from the Table 1 a vast majority of respondents (44%) fall in the age band of 36- 45 years. Out of 100 respondents 36% are between 25-35 years and 17% are between 46-55 years of age and very less 3% are above 60 years of age.

Table - 2 Educational Qualification of Respondents

Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage to the Total
Under Graduate	30	30%
Post Graduate	45	45%
Professional	19	19%
Diploma	6	6%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

It is revealed from the Table 2 that 45% of the respondents are Post Graduate, 30% are Under Graduate, and Remaining 19% and 6% are professional and diploma qualified respondents.

Table - 3 Occupation Distribution

Educational Qualification	No. of respondents	Percentage to the Total
Govt.	18	18%
Private	52	52%
Business	26	26%
Agriculture	4	4%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

It is clear from the Table 3 that 52% respondents are employees of Pvt. Sector, 26% belongs to business class, 18% respondents are from Govt. Sector and remaining are from Agriculture or other occupation.

Table- 4 Annual Income of Respondents

Annual Income	No. of respondents	Percentage to the Total
Below 50,000	40	40%
51,000- 1,00,000	31	31%
1,00,1000-1,50,000	19	19%
Above 1.51,000	10	10%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

Table 4 shows that 40% respondent have an annual income below 50,000, 31% respondent have an annual income in the range between 51,000- 1,00,000, 19% have an annual income in the range between 1,01,000- 1,50,000 and remaining 10% respondent have an annual income above 1,51,000.

Table - 5 Policies Owned by the Respondents

Annual Income	No. of respondents	Percentage to the Total
LIC	65	65%
Private	13	13%
Both	22	22%
Total	100	100

Source: Primary Data

It is clear from the above Table 5 that 65% of the respondents are having policy of LIC and 13% respondents are having policy of Pvt. Companies and 22% of the respondents are having policy of both i.e. LIC and Pvt. Companies.

Table - 6 Opinion about Various Policie Holders

Response	Strongly Agree	Agree	Natural	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Investment decisions	12	6	7	4	1
motives of getting insurance decisions	18	13	3	2	1
Customer’s preference for selecting sector	10	6	4	2	1
If any problems faced by customers	5	3	1	1	0
Percentage to total (%)	45%	28%	15%	9%	3%

It is clear from the above Table 6 that 28% and 45% respondents are Agree and Strongly Agree for comparing various policies before selecting one.

Hypothesis Testing

1. Null Hypothesis (Ho - 1): There is no significant difference regarding influencing factors for investment decisions between public and private life insurance policy holders.

Life Insurance Companies	Mean of Respondents	Standard Deviation of Respondents	Size of Sample
LIC	4.3891	.3066	76
Private company	4.1428	.3098	24

Source: Computed Primary Data

- a) Level of Significance = 5%
- b) Computed Value of Z- test for above table = 1.791

Computed value of Z- test i.e. 1.791 is less than the tabulated value which is 1.961, so null hypothesis is accepted. That means there is no difference regarding influencing factors for investment decisions between public and private life insurance policy holders i.e. company’s image, CRM, Promotional strategies, attractive schemes, variety of products, services provided and presale communication, all have equal influence on customers of public and private insurance companies.

2. Null Hypothesis (Ho - 2): There is no significant difference between the motives of getting insurance decisions between public and private life insurance policy holders.

Life Insurance Companies	Mean of Respondents	Standard Deviation of Respondents	Size of Sample
LIC	3.6778	.5994	76
Private company	3.434	.7027	24

- a) Level of Significance = 5%
- b) Computed Value of Z- test for above table = 1.3072

Computed value of Z- test i.e. 1.3072 is less than the tabulated value which is 1.961, so null hypothesis is accepted. That means there is no difference regarding the motive of getting insurance

decisions between public and private life insurance policy holders i.e. the reasons behind selecting insurance company is same whether it is for safety or for investment purpose or for tax benefits or to procure loan in future.

3. Null Hypothesis (Ho - 3): There is no significant difference between customer's preference for selecting a plan of buying public life insurance policy and private life insurance policy.

Life Insurance Companies	Mean of Respondents	Standard Deviation of Respondents	Size of Sample
LIC	4.0027	.62236	76
Private company	4.097	.22932	24

- a) Level of Significance = 5%
- b) Computed Value of Z- test for above table = -.54

Computed Value Z- test i.e. -.54 is more than the tabulated value which is -1.961, so null hypothesis is accepted. That means there is no significant difference between customer's preference for selecting a particular plan offered by public and private life insurance company.

4) Null Hypothesis (Ho - 4): There is no significant difference between the problems faced by the customers of public life insurance and private life insurance.

Life Insurance Companies	Mean of Respondents	Standard Deviation of Respondents	Size of Sample
LIC	3.293	.2482	76
Private company	2.997	.2383	24

- a) Level of Significance = 5%
- b) Computed Value of Z- test for above table = 2.398

Computed Value Z- test i.e. 2.398 is more than the tabulated value which is 1.961, so null hypothesis is rejected. That means there is significant difference between the problems' faced by the customer's of public and private life insurance companies.

Limitations of the Study

In spite of every care taken on the part of the researcher there were certain limitations which could not be overcome and are as follows:

1. Some of the respondents were not so responsive
2. Possibility of error in data collection because many of investors may have not given actual answers of my questionnaire
3. The sample size may not adequately represent the whole market
4. Some respondents were reluctant to divulge personal information which can affect the validity of all respondents

The above are some of the aspects which posed real problems in the way of completion of the research work but the majority of respondents were cooperative and my gratitude are to them.

Conclusion

The entry of private sector insurance companies into the Indian insurance sector triggered off a series of charges in the industry. Even with the stiff competition in the market place, it is evident from the study that the public sector giant LIC dominates the Indian insurance industry. Thus, it

can be inferred that though public sector dominates as per customers preference but at the same time, private players as intruders have got golden opportunity to prove themselves and acquire major market share with the strength & unique quality of simplified & timely claim settlement, formalities, procedures and accessibility of agents which is of utmost importance in life insurance sector where public sector is lacking.

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